

MuseLeader: Toward Music Editing through Time-series Semantic Parameters Control using Large Language Model

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Abstract. Designing control methods in music generation systems is essential for music generation along with user preferences. In particular, parameter control provides an effective means of adjusting the atmosphere of generated music, such as “brightness.” Additionally, some music generation systems allow users to specify transitions in atmospheric intensity. However, parameter control is constrained by the frame problem, where users can only manipulate the parameters predefined by the system. To overcome this limitation, this study proposes an approach that leverages large language models (LLMs) to allow users to define parameter meanings through text. We also introduce *MuseLeader*, a working music composition system. This is equipped with a graphical user interface supporting customization of semantically defined time-series parameters. User studies indicate that parameters with clear semantic definitions (e.g. “powerful,” “robotic”) can be effectively controlled according to user intent. Additionally, some users refine their expressive intentions through changing parameter axis. For further advancements, it is essential not only to enhance the inference capabilities of LLMs but also to explore multimodal inputs beyond text to improve the interpretation of complex and nuanced musical concepts.

Keywords: Human-in-the-loop · Music Arrangement and Composition System · Parameter Control · Large Language Model · Prompt Engineering

1 Introduction

Music composition and arrangement using AI has been a central theme since the early days of computing. Recent advances in deep learning have made it feasible to generate music from natural language descriptions¹. By allowing users to

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¹ Udio: <https://www.udio.com/>

Fig. 1. Interface of *MuseLeader*

Fig. 2. System composition of *MuseLeader*

specify moods and adjust parameters, even non-experts can enjoy composing and arranging music [8]. A critical component behind this progress lies in the interfaces to control system outputs.

Media such as music and storytelling inherently possess temporal structures, with content evolving over time. To support user control over such time-series media, **time-series semantic parameters** have been proposed. These parameters allow users to define how generated content changes across time. For instance, TaleBrush [2] enables users to manipulate a protagonist's fortune throughout a story, while SOUNDRAW² lets users adjust musical dynamics every four bars iteratively. However, existing systems [10] restrict parameter meanings to those predefined by developers, limiting flexibility and reflecting the classical *frame problem* in AI. Allowing users to freely define parameter semantics could enable more diverse and intention-aligned control over music development.

A major challenge in realizing such an interface is associating user-defined parameters with concrete editing operations. Since collecting annotated data for

² <https://soundraw.io>

training is costly, supervised learning is difficult to apply. One alternative is to leverage pretrained models with extensive world knowledge. Large Language Models (LLMs), in particular, have absorbed considerable musical knowledge from web-scale data [15]. Based on this observation, we developed a system called *Grazia Piano Tuner*, which integrates an LLM with a music renderer to support **customizable semantic parameters** [13]. While this system is equipped with a graphical user interface (GUI), its semantic parameter control was limited to global settings applied to the entire piece.

In this paper, we present a music composition system, *MuseLeader*, which extends the *Grazia Piano Tuner* by supporting **time-series customizable semantic parameters**. To address the instability in music control caused by the naive application of LLMs, we employ prompt engineering techniques to enhance output stability. We further evaluate the system via a user study, focusing on the usability of the proposed interface. Finally, we discuss limitations and challenges in applying LLMs to this domain.

2 Related Work

Recent years have witnessed rapid progress in music generation systems. Early studies explored interactive methods such as generating additional voices from a melody[5] and intervening in music generation through live performance[12]. Among these, parameter control has been one of the primary approaches in both research[8] and commercial products.³ Recent systems like SOUNDRAW have further expanded these capabilities to cover temporal structure and musical dynamics. In addition, some platforms⁴ now allow users to define the semantics of control parameters, offering greater flexibility in how users interact with generative systems. However, integrating such semantic flexibility with detailed temporal control remains an open challenge.

A key to this progress is the evolution of music generation. Many can now generate music from natural language prompts, and allow control over various aspects such as mood or melody. These models are generally divided into acoustic-based and symbolic-based approaches. Acoustic models often employ multi-modal learning[14], with some incorporating LLMs to boost performance[7]. Symbolic approaches focus on structured note sequences, using models such as LSTM[4] or more recently, Transformers[6]. Despite these advances, music editing capabilities remain limited. Some systems[17, 16] allow users to edit attributes like timbre or genre, but their flexibility is constrained by backend models. Their development is also hindered by the limited availability of annotated data. Creating and labeling large-scale audio datasets is labor-intensive and often requires expert knowledge[9]. As a result, it remains difficult to align user instructions with detailed musical operations, and supervised learning is hard to apply in this domain.

³ Flow Machines: <https://www.flow-machines.com>

⁴ MusicFX: <https://aitestkitchen.withgoogle.com/tools/music-fx>

Large language models (LLMs) have begun to address these challenges. By interpreting user instructions and planning content modifications[17], LLMs help better align outputs with user intent. Recent studies show that LLMs can acquire musical knowledge and reasoning skills, and can generate music in text format[15]. Leveraging LLMs may enable parameter control with arbitrary semantics, potentially bypassing the need for explicit alignment between user instructions and low-level musical operations. Motivated by these prospects, we are investigating the use of LLMs for musical arrangement tasks[13].

3 Grazia Piano Tuner

In this section, we outline the composition system *Grazia Piano Tuner*, the base system for *MuseLeader* presented in this paper. A demonstration of the system is available on a video-sharing platform.⁵

Grazia Piano Tuner is an LLM-based system for interactive composition and arrangement. It generates music based on user instructions, plays the resulting tracks, and displays them in a piano roll. Users can issue commands to modify the music and adjust its overall mood using a **customizable semantic parameter**, with values ranging from -1 to 1. The meaning of this parameter, referred to as the **parameter axis**, can be defined by the user, allowing control over musical characteristics such as “brightness” or “jazziness.”

The LLM interprets user input and applies changes to the music. A pre-configured prompt guides the LLM to generate or edit music according to parameter values. User input is passed to the LLM, which generates MIDI for audio playback. Because LLMs are text-based, music must be represented in textual formats for editing. On the web, formats such as ABC notation⁶ and MusicXML⁷ are widely available, and LLMs are likely trained on such data[15]. However, current LLMs still struggle with reliable music generation, sometimes producing incorrect formats for complex pieces. This problem was partially mitigated by using `gpt-4o-2024-05-13` and ABC notation, but output stability remains an issue.

To enhance generation stability, the LLM must be equipped with additional knowledge of the notation. Prompt engineering was applied to address this. Although this process is typically exploratory, we picked up and evaluated four techniques to improve its stability. For each technique, we generated approximately 100 music outputs and assessed how often the correct format was produced. The evaluation revealed several key findings. Stability improved when the LLM was given examples of the expected output or a rule set to suppress errors. However, asking the LLM to review its own output for mistakes had the opposite effect. By applying these techniques, we successfully reduced the rate of incorrect formats from 23% to 9%.

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ubhIFUJPtFQ>

⁶ <https://abcnotation.com/wiki/abc:standard:v2.1>

⁷ <https://www.musicxml.com>

To conduct a subjective evaluation of the system’s editing capabilities and user experience, we carried out a user study ($N = 10$) and a larger-scale evaluation of parameter performance ($N = 110$). Results showed that while the system enables flexible editing of various musical elements, there is still room for improvement in performance and interface design. Participants reported that parameters such as “brightness,” “spring,” and “solemn” produced natural-sounding changes in tonality, tempo, and chord progression. However, genre-specific controls (e.g., “jazz” or “swing”) were less effective, failing to capture distinctive melodic and harmonic features. Users expected more dramatic changes at the maximum parameter values, but the output didn’t reflect this. This highlights the need to better match the system’s maximum settings to user expectations. The system also does not support editing specific time segments or measures, which hinders temporal parameter control. To address these challenges, we are developing a new system, *MuseLeader*, which will be introduced in the next chapter.

4 MuseLeader

In this section, we describe the implementation of *MuseLeader*, a system that enables music control using time-series semantic parameters. A video demonstration of this application is available on a video sharing site⁸.

4.1 Interface Design

Figure 1 shows the interface of the system. Time-series semantic parameters provide an interface to capture the evolution of a musical piece over time by specifying a mood and its intensity transition. Users adjust the mood’s intensity at different time points by dragging circular markers (Figure 1(b)), and they determine a **parameter axis** by entering its name in the text box (Figure 1(a)). For example, entering “brightness” instructs the system to manage changes in the music’s brightness.

When the submit button is pressed, the system generates a musical piece with both a melody and a chord progression, assigning instruments accordingly. If users modify parameters after generation, the system updates only the relevant sections while preserving the overall motif. Parameters are defined for every four measures. This unit length aligns with common musical structures, such as cadences, which often span four measures. Shorter units may miss harmonic meaning and lead to unstable control with LLMs, while longer ones reduce control granularity. The parameter range is initially set between $m = 0$ and $M = 1$, but users can input values beyond these limits. In such cases, the system automatically extends the range to accommodate the new values. This allows the system to align with user intentions.

⁸ <https://youtu.be/2NiXcWNXUzw>

4.2 Implementation

In this study, we developed a workflow for generating and editing music based on time-series customizable semantic parameters. Figure 2 illustrates the configuration of the system. The system operates as follows: 1) it accepts input of time-series semantic parameters, which can be specified for every four measures; 2) it sends the input information to a LLM with instruction stating “Generate and edit music based on the given parameters.” In our implementation, we utilized `gpt-4o-2024-08-06` and ABC notation as writing format. 3) the LLM generates and edits music while referencing previous inputs and outputs; and 4) text output from the LLM is converted into MIDI format by `abc2midi`⁹. This allows the user to audition the MIDI data, visualize it in a piano roll format. Finally, 5) users provide additional instructions. Through these steps, we built an interactive interface for music composition and arrangement.

This study focuses on the generation and editing of melodies, chord progressions, and instrument selection. This approach is feasible because ABC notation provides a grammar for representing both melodies and chord progressions, and `abc2midi` supports specifying performance instruments in the ABC format by `%%MIDI program` instructions. More complex accompaniment and audio mixing will be handled by other tools.

In the base system, *Grazia Piano Tuner*, we stabilized music generation by providing concrete examples and additional knowledge in the LLM’s prompts. While effective for controlling overall structure, this approach showed limitations in time-series control. Specifying measure ranges and requesting changes to melody or harmony often led to unintended edits in unrelated sections, disrupting the intended progression. To address this, we refined our use of the LLM to better support localized control. In the following, we highlight several key improvements. The full details of the prompt are available on the support site¹⁰.

The composition process is divided into specialized tasks, each of which is assigned to a dedicated LLM agent (leader, chord, melody, and instrument). This role-based structure improves controllability in the generation process [3]. The system takes as input a table specifying parameter names and their values for each four-measure segment. The leader agent interprets the temporal transitions of these parameters and outputs a structured plan that describes musical elements (e.g. melody, instrumentation) every four measures. This plan guides the subsequent agents in their respective generation tasks. Based on the leader’s output, the chord agent generates a 16-measure chord progression, with up to two chords per measure. The melody agent then generates a melody in ABC notation, referencing both the chord progression and the structural plan. To enhance stability, the prompt incorporates techniques adapted from *Grazia Piano Tuner*. Finally, the instrument agent annotates the ABC format with instrumentation information using `abc2midi`. It inserts `%%MIDI program` commands every four measures to specify instruments for melody, harmony, and bass parts, based on the leader’s plan. Given revised user input, regeneration proceeds through the

⁹ <https://abcmidi.sourceforge.io>

¹⁰ <https://appbird.github.io/muse-leader/>

Fig. 3. Workflow of LLM-Based Music Composition and Arrangement

same pipeline. Each agents consults its previous input-output history and applies updates only to the modified segments.

We evaluated the effectiveness of the above improvements as follows. For this experiment, we used the 10 major genre names from MusicCaps¹¹ as parameter axes. We defined success as a change in the melody, chord progression, or instrumentation within the intended section when a parameter was adjusted. For each axis, we conducted ten trials, generating music with the LLMs and then randomly varying parameter values for regeneration. Before the improvements, editing failed in 17% of cases, but this dropped to 9% after applying our prompt engineering. This results confirm the effectiveness of our approach.

5 User Study

In this section, we describe a user study conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the time-series customizable semantic parameters, along with the feedback collected from participants. The generated music is available for listening on the support page (see footnote 10).

5.1 Experiment Setup

Participants received an explanation of how the system operates and were given 30 minutes to freely interact with it. During this time, they repeatedly input semantic parameters and listened to the generated or edited musical pieces. After each composition, participants were asked whether the generated music aligned with their intended input. After the interaction session, participants took part

¹¹ <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/googleai/musiccaps>

Table 1. Classification of Semantic Axes Used in User Study

Rating	Semantic Axes (Users)
high	Powerful (p_3, p_4), Robotic (p_3, p_4), Uplifting (p_3, p_4), Violent (p_1), Calm (p_1), Passionate (p_2), Majestic (p_2)
middle	Brightness ($p_1, p_2, p_5, p_6, p_7, p_8$), Classical ($p_3, p_4, p_5, p_6, p_7, p_8$), Fairy-tale (p_5, p_6, p_7, p_8), Gentle (p_1), Solemn (p_1), Urban (p_2), Soft (p_2)
low	Touching (p_3, p_4), Heart-Pounding (p_3, p_4), Childlike (p_1), Transparent (p_2), Popular (p_2), Beethoven-like (p_2)

in a semi-structured interview lasting 10 - 15 minutes. In the interview, they rated their level of agreement with several statements regarding the system’s controllability on a 5-point Likert scale. The statements focused on:

1. Whether the direction and magnitude of the parameter control matched the editing content.
2. Whether the controlled sections corresponded to the edited sections of the musical piece.
3. Whether the editing process met their expectations.

Additionally, participants were asked to explain the reasons for their ratings.

5.2 Feedback

A total of $N = 8$ participants (p_1 through p_8) took part in the study. Participants p_1, p_3, p_5 , and p_6 were new to music, while p_2, p_4, p_7 , and p_8 had over 8 years of musical experience¹².

Table 1 presents the semantic parameter axes evaluated by participants in our study. We first sorted the axes by their average ratings, then partitioned them into three clusters according to how closely users felt the system’s output matched their intentions. The table also indicates which participants contributed to each cluster. Key insights from this analysis are summarized below.

Musical Generation: 7 participants noted that the generated melody and chord progression did not feel discordant and were correctly controlled according to the parameters. All participants highly appreciated the system’s ability to assign instruments. For example, when p_4 specified a “robotic” character, the system selected a synthetic sound for segments with high parameter values and an acoustic piano for segments with low parameter values. This differentiation was well received. However, according to p_2 , the melody sometimes contained dissonant notes, and many edits were made simply by changing the instrument. p_2 also noted that complex chords, such as augmented chords, did not appear unless explicitly specified as the parameter axis. Additionally, p_4 observed that

¹² Participants (p_3, p_4) and (p_5, p_6, p_7, p_8) interacted with the system collaboratively as teams. For p_2 , the years of experience refer to time spent studying music theory, while for p_4, p_7 , and p_8 , they indicate years of experience playing an keyboard instruments.

while there was coherence within each four-measure segment, the overall piece lacked cohesion beyond these segments. p_4 also commented on examples that lacked a sense of cadence.

Time-Series Semantic Parameter Control: Seven participants noticed that the music changed in the segments where the time-series parameters were adjusted. and they also evaluated the direction of the parameter change and found it consistent with the music editing strategy. The system supports control over four-measure segments. p_1 , p_2 , p_4 , and p_6 expressed a desire for control at a finer resolution. In particular, p_4 stated a preference for control at the level of individual notes. However, p_7 and p_8 stated that controlling by four-measure segments was easier to understand, indicating a divergence of opinions among participants.

Customizable Parameter Axis: After generating music using the axis “calmness,” participant p_1 proceeded to experiment with additional axes such as “childlikeness” and “solemnity.” He noted that changing the parameter axis during the editing process allowed him to incorporate new expressive directions into the music. However, all participants reported difficulty when using more abstract or emotionally nuanced axes, such as “urbanity,” “heart-pounding,” and “touching.” None of the generated outputs under these conditions aligned with their expectations. Participant p_1 remarked, “The generated music did not match the exact image I had in mind,” while p_4 stated, “I wish the system could provide an answer even when the axis is something I don’t fully understand.” Participant p_3 further noted that the effectiveness varied significantly across different semantic axes, describing the gap between well-aligned and poorly-aligned outputs as “striking.” We discuss this issue in the next chapter.

6 Discussion

6.1 Toward More Expressive User Interface

Time-series parameters enable a more accurate expression of the user’s intentions than fixed-meaning parameter control. For instance, parameter p_1 first switched the parameter axis to “childlikeness.” Later, it changed the axis to “solemnity” and increased the parameter values to remove the “clumsiness” which appeared in sections emphasizing childlikeness. This approach demonstrated that replacing the parameter axis can reconcile the difference between the system’s interpretation and the user’s intent.

There are limitations to conveying the intended meaning of an axis solely through text. Among the axes users interacted with, those representing relatively straightforward concepts, such as “powerful,” “robotic,” or “uplifting,” were effectively controlled. In contrast, for more complex concepts and styles, including “Beethoven-like,” “Urban,” and “touching,” user intentions were not well reflected in the generated results. This issue stems partly from the performance limitations of the underlying model. Controlling these types of axes requires a deeper understanding of musical elements such as chord progressions and stylistic conventions, which current LLMs struggle to handle. In addition, a single parameter

axis may correspond to multiple musical styles, further complicating interpretation. When the meaning of an axis is too ambiguous, the generated music may deviate significantly from the user’s intended direction. Simply replacing the axis does not necessarily help in aligning it with the user’s intent. To more accurately capture user intentions, it may be necessary to incorporate modalities beyond text. For instance, an interface that allows users to specify a reference musical piece as input [11] could be a potential solution.

Many participants expressed a desire for a higher time resolution, with some even wishing to control the parameter on a per-note basis. If the control unit can be made sufficiently fine-grained, the parameter values could be specified continuously. This would enable to control the parameters by drawing curves, as in TaleBrush [2]. However, if the control unit is too fine, the meaning of the parameters may lose interpretability. For example, a “jazz feel” emerges from the relationships among multiple notes and rhythms, so at the single-note level it is difficult to express the parameter. The appropriate length of control may also vary depending on the parameter axis. There remains room for discussion regarding how continuous time-series input should be interpreted by the machine. Although adding a function to adjust the control unit itself might be a solution, careful interface design is required to avoid confusing the user.

6.2 Toward More Intention-Aware Control

The system appears to have acquired the ability for time-series control primarily due to two factors: reducing the complexity of the task for individual roles, and the inclusion of markers in the score that indicate the measure number for each line. Current LLMs are capable of capturing relationships between token positions and content within a sequence using the attention mechanism in Transformers. By incorporating such markers into the musical score, the LLM can accurately identify the sections that require editing. However, these techniques are not perfect. The generation of a musical piece can take over a minute, which hinders smooth and interactive editing with the user. Reducing this time would speedup aligning the system’s output with the user’s intent.

It has also been noted that the generated musical pieces often lack sufficient diversity and cohesion. This is likely due to the fact that the LLM does not perform enough internal reasoning during the generation of chords and melodies. However, the current prompts already ensure both generation stability and controllability of the time-series parameters. Even when the melody agent is encouraged to think step-by-step, it tends to ignore such instructions. One potential solution would be to divide the work of the melody role into multiple roles. However, this would further increase generation time. Therefore, the approach of interacting solely with the LLM requires further improvements in its reasoning capabilities.

In our approach, LLM was used to identify the necessary edits to the music based on the parameter axis. However, if alternative methods continue to advance, there may be breakthroughs beyond LLM-based approaches. In image generation, researchers have implemented customizable semantic parameters by

exploring latent spaces. In music, some models link specific dimensions of the latent space to distinct musical attributes [1]. However, implementing customizable semantic parameters for music introduces domain-specific challenges. One must ensure temporal consistency. It is also essential to identify which musical characteristics should remain unchanged during editing. Addressing these issues could also benefit the MML approach.

6.3 Limitation & Future Work

There are several limitations to this study. As a direction for future work, since there is no guarantee that the prompt engineering we employed is optimal, further refinement and quantitative evaluation are necessary. In addition, we categorized the parameter axes used by participants (Table 1) and discussed editing tendencies based on these categories. However, these discussions are qualitative, and a more accurate assessment of the system’s capabilities will require quantitative analysis. Furthermore, as the reasoning capabilities of LLMs continue to improve, it may become possible to support more advanced generation and editing without relying on carefully crafted prompts. For example, the OpenAI’s o3-mini model has overcome several issues previously encountered when generating ABC notation with traditional LLMs.

In addition to the approaches described above, other methods to better align with the user’s intent can be explored. One such approach is to have multiple LLMs engage in reflection with one another, collaboratively refining the musical piece. We are continuing to investigate this strategy to align the generated music with users’ ideals, and we plan to further develop this method in future work.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed **time-series customizable semantic parameters** as a method for controlling the progression of musical pieces and examined an implementation approach that utilizes prompt engineering with LLMs. Through a user study, we clarified the advantages and challenges of this user interface, as well as the implementation barriers encountered when using LLMs. The proposed interface shows potential for facilitating the alignment of user intent, and in certain cases, the time-series control was verified to work correctly. However, control was insufficient for parameter axes with inherent ambiguity, and there remains room for improvement in the user interface itself. In the future, we plan to investigate methods to enhance the quality of generated music through reflection among LLMs, as well as explore approaches that leverage latent space representations.

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